

PROBONO

D8.2 Dissemination and communication strategy & reporting (II)

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PROBONO

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DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximise the economic and social cobenefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardised framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

¹ Please refer to the last submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions

² <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

³ European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

⁴ SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

⁵ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 5 Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁶ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/20012018/2001

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

Table of contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	9
1 INTRODUCTION	10
1.1 MAPPING PROBONO OUTPUTS.....	10
1.2 PURPOSE AND SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT.....	11
1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT AND ITS RELATION WITH OTHER WPs/DELIVERABLES.....	11
1.4 CONTRIBUTION TO GBN CONCEPT	12
2 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & OBJECTIVES	13
2.1 INTERNAL COMMUNICATION.....	13
2.2 CALL FOR ACTION	14
3 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS & ACTIVITIES	17
3.1 WEBSITE	17
3.1.1 <i>Traffic Overview</i>	21
3.2 SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS	23
3.2.1 <i>LinkedIn</i>	23
3.2.2 <i>X</i>	26
3.3 NEWSLETTER.....	27
3.4 PRESS RELEASES	30
3.5 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS.....	33
3.6 VIDEOS	34
3.7 COMMUNICATION KIT.....	35
4 IMPACT OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES IN THE SECOND AND THIRD REPORTING PERIODS	37
5 CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS.....	39
REFERENCES.....	40
APPENDIX	41
APPENDIX I	41
APPENDIX II	42

Table of Figures

FIGURE 1 - CALL FOR ACTION.....	14
FIGURE 2 - CALL FOR ACTION #1	15
FIGURE 3 - CALL FOR ACTION #2	16
FIGURE 4 - PROBONO WEBSITE.....	17
FIGURE 5: CERNA WEBPAGE I	18

FIGURE 6: CERNA WEBPAGE II	19
FIGURE 7: AARHUS LIVING LAB WEBPAGE.....	20
FIGURE 8 - WEBSITE TRAFFIC OVERVIEW (M9-M23)	21
FIGURE 9 - WEBSITE TRAFFIC OVERVIEW (M24 - M35).....	21
FIGURE 10 - BEHAVIOUR OVERVIEW (M9 – M23).....	22
FIGURE 11 - BEHAVIOUR OVERVIEW (M24 – M35).....	23
FIGURE 12: LINKEDIN PAGE	24
FIGURE 13 - LINKEDIN IMPRESSIONS RATE	25
FIGURE 14: VISITOR DEMOGRAPHICS	25
FIGURE 15: X PAGE	26
FIGURE 16: X IMPRESSIONS RATE.....	27
FIGURE 17 - NEWSLETTER HEADER	29
FIGURE 18: PROJECT VIDEO	34
FIGURE 19 - PROJECT PRESENTATION.....	36
FIGURE 20 - PROBONO ROLL UP V2	41
FIGURE 21 - PROBONO STICKER V1.....	42

List of tables

TABLE 1: ADHERENCE TO PROBONO'S GA DELIVERABLE & TASKS DESCRIPTIONS.....	11
TABLE 2 - PRESS RELEASES	33
TABLE 3 - SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS.....	34
TABLE 4 - KPI LIST.....	38

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
CC	Communication Committee
GBN	Green Building Neighbourhood
SM	Social media
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
TL	Task Leader
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The D8.2 report meticulously evaluates PROBONO's achievements against its commitments in the Grant Agreement, with a focus on Communication and Dissemination (C&D) strategy. This assessment spans up to M35, comparing planned activities from D8.1 against realized outcomes and proposing enhancements for future strategies.

It outlines the C&D strategy's evolution, emphasizing the shift from initial project awareness to showcasing materials, fostering stakeholder interest, and exploiting project results. The report highlights the pivotal role of the Communication Committee in facilitating effective coordination among partners.

The report comprehensively covers website updates, social media performance, newsletter engagement, press releases, scientific publications, and video productions. Key highlights include successful mandated press releases, robust engagement on LinkedIn and X, and effective dissemination of project videos across multiple channels. The report also outlines the creation of a comprehensive communication kit and presents detailed Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) aligned with project goals.

Looking forward, the report identifies priorities for the next phase (M36–M42). These include amplifying the visibility of Social Innovation and Living Lab initiatives through digital marketing and emphasizing technological advancements integral to the project. By highlighting these areas, the next phase aims to strengthen PROBONO's impact and further enhance stakeholder engagement and dissemination efforts.

1 Introduction

1.1 Mapping PROBONO Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map PROBONO's GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed. D8.2 (Dissemination & Communication Strategy & Reporting (II)) addresses Task 8.1 (Dissemination Strategy, Communication Plan and Activities) which consists of ST8.1.1 (Dissemination Strategy & Communication Plan), ST8.1.2 (Dissemination & Communication material), and ST8.1.3 (Dissemination & Communication activities). Out of these three subtasks, D8.2C mainly handles the requirements of ST8.1.3 (Dissemination & Communication activities). The primary purpose of ST8.1.3 is to effectively communicate the innovations, KPIs, and results of the PROBONO project to diverse audiences, including local communities, stakeholders, and academic circles, through various communication channels, localization, and collaborative efforts, ensuring widespread awareness and utilization of the project's outcomes.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 8.1. Dissemination Strategy, Communication Plan and Activities (M1-M60)	<p>ST8.1.3. Dissemination & Communication activities.</p> <p>Promotional campaigns will be created. The project LL innovations and KPIs will be published, using the project web presence and the communication channels established in ST8.1.2. Communication actions are targeting a diverse set of audiences and external stakeholders, to increase the impact, selected content will be localised (translated). Presentations at national and international conferences and collaboration with other research projects and initiatives will lead to potential synergies, best practises, and the creation of new knowledge. The actions to foreseen are: (a) Communication packages designed as per local communication strategies for Living Labs such as local promotional events, using pilot Living Lab content, where ICT engagement tool WP2 and dashboards from WP5 will be demonstrated. Also, school visits will be scheduled to educate the new generation about the PROBONO approach. (b) Communication material for broader audience, including press releases on initial/main results, and a presentation to be used by the partners and pilots for</p>	Chapter 2-5 and Annexes I-II	Communication and Dissemination activities are described along with the communication objectives, & strategy, activities & tools, impact, and plan for the next period.

	<p>presenting the PROBONO results at meetings, conferences. During and towards end of the project, communication package (presentations, marketing material etc.) will be developed and updated to follow the key findings and results tailored for the project partners' own use enabling them to exploit the project work during and post-PROBONO. The final communication package will include video(s), which document the results of the project, to be published on the web, including social media and streaming channels. (c) Scientific publications/papers made during the project will be coordinated.</p>		
DELIVERABLE			
<p>D8.2: Dissemination and Communication Strategy & Reporting (II) Report of communication and dissemination activities in RP II and III</p>			

Table 1: Adherence to PROBONO's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

1.2 Purpose and scope of the document

The purpose of this deliverable is to assess the progress of implemented activities and revise the communication and dissemination strategy for the project, using the D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy & Reporting (I) as a reference to compare the planned activities with the actual progress up to M35. This report analyses the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) efforts based on feedback and KPI measurements from Reporting Period II and III, and it also proposes mitigation actions to address current challenges and improve the effectiveness of communication and dissemination strategy for the upcoming period.

This deliverable is directly connected to the D8.1 Dissemination and communication strategy & reporting (I), and it also makes references to two other deliverables, D8.5 Liaison Activities and Event Participation (I), and D8.6 Liaison Activities and Event Participation (II), both falling within Task 8.2 (PROBONO Liaison Activities). These references are made to highlight the coordination efforts with other EU projects and the plan for participating in events.

1.3 Structure of the document and its relation with other WPs/Deliverables

This document commences by presenting the communication and dissemination strategy, along with the communication objectives in Section 2. Subsequently, in Section 3, a comprehensive report is provided, detailing the communication and dissemination activities undertaken and the outcomes achieved up to M35. Section 3 also includes an overview of the tools that have been utilized for communication and dissemination activities during the past 35 months. Moving

forward, the assessment of the impact resulting from these communication and dissemination efforts and tools is addressed in Section 4. Finally, in Section 5, the conclusions drawn and the proposed action plans to be implemented over the next two years are highlighted.

1.4 Contribution to GBN Concept

The deliverable encompasses the description, assessment, and enhancement of the communication and dissemination tools and activities aimed at advancing the GBN concept. These efforts involve promoting the established GBN concept, its development, and achievements through diverse means like active participation in both national and international events, the utilization of social media platforms, the project website, regular newsletters, etc.

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy & Objectives

Before delving into the comprehensive evaluation and reporting of Dissemination and Communication activities from Month 9 to Month 35, it is important to highlight the main objectives behind the Communication and Dissemination strategy within the PROBONO project, initially formulated in D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy & Reporting (I). This strategy primarily centres on the design of initiatives aimed at establishing a coherent and engaging storyline for the PROBONO project. The strategy is intended to serve as the fundamental framework for project participants and consortium members when delivering speeches, presenting the project, or participating in various events.

In the initial project year, communication efforts were centred on raising awareness of the project's objectives, scope, and planned activities to attract the interest of stakeholders. In the second year, the focus transitioned to presenting the materials created and generating new content to maintain stakeholder engagement and interest, while also gathering essential feedback. This emphasis on showcasing materials and fostering stakeholder interest, along with feedback collection, persisted into the third year. Finally, in the project's final years, the primary emphasis will be on exploiting the project's results, ensuring its continuity after the funding period concludes, and devising a strategy for market entry and replication.

2.1 Internal Communication

As previously outlined in D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy & Reporting (I), the PROBONO project formed a Communication Committee to implement the established Communication and Dissemination Strategy. This Communication Committee has been serving as a unit to support the communication and dissemination activities of the project. Each partner designated one or two representatives to be part of the Communication Committee who took a responsibility for collecting information and input from their own organization which were then relayed and distributed by the WP8 leader on digital and traditional communication platforms.

The Communication Committee was entrusted with the following responsibilities:

- Aiding in the writing and editing of articles for PROBONO's external newsletters.
- Regularly updating the events list, encompassing international, national, and local events, to maintain clear oversight of participant involvement and prepare essential communication materials in advance.

- Delivering content to the WP8 leader for publication on the project's website, newsletters, or social media channels, in accordance with the Content Creation Schedule and Content Creation Guideline. To facilitate the work, WP8 leader established a new Content Creation Schedule for the Communication Committee on an annual basis, alongside a simplified Content Creation Guideline.
- Contributing insights and feedback towards the development of visual materials for the project.
- Collaborating on the formulation of scripts for project videos.

To ensure effective coordination, the Communication Committee convened in monthly meetings, with participation from the WP8 leader and representatives from each partner.

2.2 Call for Action

In the second project year, PROBONO was set to enhance its Call for Action, recognizing the evolving project needs and objectives. The refined Call for Action is a compelling invitation, urging stakeholders to actively participate in the development of sustainable communities/neighbourhoods.

Call for Action

- Join us in building a sustainable future! Be an active participant in shaping and supporting Green Building Neighborhoods. Embrace green practices, collaborate with Living Labs, and advocate for inclusive, sustainable communities. Together, let's create a positive impact on society and the environment:
 1. **Active Participation:** Stakeholders are expected to actively participate in the design, construction, and operation of Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs). This involves contributing ideas, insights, and efforts towards creating sustainable and energy-positive communities.
 2. **Adoption of Sustainable Practices:** The project anticipates stakeholders to adopt and promote sustainable practices within their communities. This includes embracing green energy, green mobility, and environmentally friendly infrastructure at the district level.
 3. **Support and Collaboration:** Stakeholders are encouraged to support the GBN Transition Acceleration Enablers deployed in the Living Labs across EU states. This involves collaborating with the project's initiatives, especially within the designated Living Labs, to facilitate the transition to green neighbourhoods.
 4. **Participation in Co-Design and Co-Delivery:** The project emphasizes the importance of stakeholders, including citizens, participating in co-designing and co-delivering sustainable GBNs. The input and involvement of various stakeholders are valued in shaping the design and implementation process.
 5. **Advocacy and Promotion:** Stakeholders are expected to advocate for the adoption of the PROBONO approach and innovations in creating sustainable communities. This includes spreading awareness, promoting the benefits, and encouraging the adoption of these practices and technologies.

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Figure 1 - Call for Action

The revamped call emphasizes the importance of collaboration, sustainable practices, and advocacy in shaping GBNs. The project highlights five key areas, encouraging stakeholders to

actively engage in the design, construction, and operation of GBNs, adopt sustainable practices, support Living Labs' initiatives, actively participate in co-design and co-delivery processes, and advocate for the adoption of PROBONO's approach and innovations. This enhanced Call for Action was integrated into the content developed by PROBONO's Communication Committee, disseminated across various digital and traditional communication platforms, fostering greater engagement and commitment among stakeholders.

In addition to the overarching Call for Action guiding the PROBONO project's initiatives, specific Calls for Action were employed within the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) activities. PROBONO continues to leverage specific Calls for Action within its C&D activities. These encompass directives like encouraging engagement through social media channels, inviting individuals to explore the project's website for comprehensive information, and prompting subscription to the project's newsletter. The project actively employs these Calls for Action to prompt audience interaction and engagement across various communication platforms. Detailed examples showcasing the implementation of these Calls for Action during the initial reporting period can be found in the figures below.

Figure 2 - Call for Action #1

ProbonoH2020
471 followers
2mo · Edited · 🗨️

In Progress Update 📅

👀 Curious about what's brewing in the world of construction innovation? We're here to give you a sneak peek into an exciting work-in-progress tool!

🔍 The PROBONO project's consortium member, **Aarhus University**, has been tackling a crucial issue in the architecture and construction industry.

The Problem:
👷 Architects invest extensive thought and effort into designing buildings with specific social values. But all too often, these intentions get lost in the shuffle when passed on to other stakeholders in the design team.

🌱 Introducing ProBIM—an ingenious solution that's currently under development. Our goal is to digitize design intention arguments and seamlessly integrate them into the digital representation of buildings, known as the BIM model. This will allow stakeholders to understand:

- 🔧 "What" design changes are implemented.
- 👤 "Why" these changes are crucial for social value.
- 🛠️ "How" these design alterations will achieve that value.

ProBIM will ensure that these crucial design intention arguments and social values remain present in the BIM model, safeguarding them from being lost or misinterpreted when shared with others. 🌐

📝 We're taking steady strides towards completing demos and fine-tuning this innovative tool. Stay tuned for more updates as we journey toward revolutionizing the construction industry!

Learn More 📄
🔗 <https://lnkd.in/dmQfYKnU>

#ProBIM #DesignInnovation #GBN #GreenBuildingNeighbourhood #H2020

ProBIM: Revolutionizing Building Design and Social Value Preservation...
youtube.com

👤 Ketil Thomsen and 39 others 3 comments · 3 reposts

ProbonoH2020
471 followers
4mo · 🗨️

Exciting News from PROBONO Brussels Living Lab! 📅

We're thrilled to share the success of our recent PROBONO Discovery event, brought to you by our amazing Consortium member, #ACE! 🌟

📅 On Friday, 9th June, from 5 p.m. to 7 p.m., our school opened its doors to students, teachers, parents, and neighbors, all eager to dive into the world of the European H2020 Probono project. This groundbreaking project, which commenced in 2022, is committed to shaping a future of sustainable and connected communities through innovative energy-efficient buildings. 🌱🏡

We're proud to have ACE on board as a driving force behind this endeavor. Their dedication and enthusiasm have helped steer us towards success, and their role in making PROBONO project a reality is truly commendable. 🙌

Stay connected with us to stay updated on our journey of transformation and sustainability. Let's continue to collaborate and innovate for a greener, more connected future! 🌍

Curious about our Living Labs? Learn more here: https://hubs.ly/Q01_0_3k0

#GreenBuildingNeighbourhood #GBN #Brussels #BrusselsLivingLab

👤 Javier Antolin Gutiérrez and 25 others 2 comments · 3 reposts

Figure 3 - Call for Action #2

3 Communication and Dissemination Tools & Activities

The upcoming section provides an overview of the communication and dissemination efforts carried out until M35, encompassing progress reports on various activities and the tools utilized to advance the PROBONO message. Furthermore, detailed updates on the activities such as event participation, alliance and liaison were presented in D8.6 PROBONO Alliance Liaison (II).

3.1 Website

The PROBONO project's website (www.probonoh2020.eu), launched in M9, serves as a central platform for sharing key information and updates with stakeholders and the public. The initial structure and objectives of the website were defined in deliverables D8.15 Project Visual Identity and D8.1 Communication and Dissemination Strategy and Reporting (I), providing a foundation for its continuous development. This section highlights recent updates to the website's content and provides an overview of its visitor engagement statistics.

Figure 4 - PROBONO Website

In M12, the website was enhanced with the addition of a dedicated "News" webpage. This new section has been instrumental in sharing a variety of articles and updates about the project's progress and milestones, ensuring timely and transparent communication with its audience. The webpage is regularly updated, reflecting the project's ongoing activities and achievements.

Looking ahead, a new webpage focusing on the PROBONO social innovation tool developed by WP2 (Social and Behavioural Innovation), CERNA Assessment (Climate and Energy Related Norms and Attitudes), is planned for publication in M36. This section will include general information about CERNA and its role in the project, along with subpages dedicated to each Living Lab. These subpages will present localized assessment results in the respective languages of the Living Labs, further supporting the project's commitment to tailored, inclusive communication.

Figure 5: CERNA Webpage I

If you are curious about the situation in other countries, you can check out the results from PROBONO's Living Labs by choosing a country.

Figure 6: CERNA Webpage II

Furthermore, modifications have been made to the content of the existing webpages:

- To begin with, the video background featured on the homepage has been replaced with a scene extracted from the project video. (Figure 4)
- An interactive gadget has been integrated onto the homepage, showcasing live posts from the main social channel of the project, LinkedIn. (Figure 4)
- The Reports page has been populated with a comprehensive list of submitted public deliverables (both pending and approved), published scientific works and project videos.
- Moreover, communication (printing) materials and newsletters are also available for download on this page.
- The subpages for each PROBONO Living Lab have been updated with detailed information that outlines the objectives and anticipated impacts of each respective Living Lab. Enhancements are planned for these pages in the forthcoming months, which will include more comprehensive details regarding the development of the Living Labs and the addition of live photographs to provide real-time insights into their progress. (Figure 7)
- Finally, an important addition includes a prominent button on the website's homepage that directs users to the Mail Chimp newsletter subscription form. This feature enables visitors to voluntarily join the PROBONO community, keeping them informed about our latest updates and significant milestones.

Figure 7: Aarhus Living Lab Webpage

3.1.1 Traffic Overview

The PROBONO website's performance data, collected via the Wix platform, is outlined below, with information from M9 to M23 and from M24 to M35 presented separately for clarity and ease of analysis. This structured approach ensures a clear understanding of the website's impact and facilitates data-driven decisions for future improvements. Wix serves as the platform for hosting the PROBONO website and gathers data to generate informative reports.

Figure 8 - Website Traffic Overview (M9-M23)

Figure 9 - Website Traffic Overview (M24 - M35)

The primary metric for assessing website traffic is the number of visits. A breakdown of website users is provided in Figure 8 and 9. Over the span of M9-M23, a total of 1,757 users visited the PROBONO website, resulting in 3,482 site sessions. These figures demonstrate a strong performance, successfully meeting the defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for this period. This level of engagement reflects the effectiveness of the project’s dissemination activities,

ensuring consistent visibility among target audiences. As the project progresses, this solid foundation positions the website as a key platform for promoting the next phase of activities and expanding stakeholder reach. The average session duration on the website was 5 minutes and 41 seconds, which is considered a strong indicator of user engagement, as it suggests visitors are spending meaningful time exploring the content. Of these users, 60% accessed the website directly, while the remaining visitors arrived via various channels, including Google, LinkedIn, website referrals, among others.

In the subsequent months 24 to 35, the website experienced a slight increase in traffic, with 1,913 unique users contributing to 3,596 sessions. Engagement metrics also improved, with the average session duration rising to 6 minutes and 22 seconds. During this period, direct traffic represented 45% of total visits, while a higher proportion of visitors accessed the site through external platforms, highlighting the growing reach and visibility of the PROBONO project across multiple digital channels.

Figure 10 - Behaviour Overview (M9 – M23)

Examining the webpages with the highest traffic on the website, the homepage emerged as the most frequently viewed page, with 2,381 site sessions during M9 – M23 and with 2,354 site sessions during M24 – M35, followed by the "About," "Pilots," and "Members" pages.

Figure 11 - Behaviour Overview (M24 – M35)

3.2 Social Media Channels

Social media has been instrumental in raising awareness and engaging audiences for the PROBONO project. As outlined in the Dissemination and Communication Strategy (D8.1), a collaborative approach was adopted to ensure a steady flow of engaging and informative content. Members of the Communication Committee worked together to collect, share, and evaluate updates, creating a seamless process for content creation. Each consortium partner played a vital role by contributing news about events, milestones, and project highlights, which were compiled and published. This coordinated effort was guided by a structured content schedule, ensuring a consistent presence on social media and effectively showcasing the project's progress.

Between M11 and M35, this strategy resulted in the publication of 249 posts across the project's social media platforms, helping to build an engaged online community of 770 followers. Notifications accompanying each post further boosted visibility and ensured stakeholders stayed informed about the project's achievements. By combining teamwork, thoughtful planning, and regular updates, the PROBONO project successfully enhanced its digital presence and strengthened connections with its audience.

3.2.1 LinkedIn

Throughout the period from M11 to M35, LinkedIn emerged as the primary social media platform for highlighting crucial project-related information within the PROBONO project. This

encompassed a spectrum of pivotal updates, including event participation, newsletters, news articles, and project milestones. With 666 followers, the PROBONO LinkedIn page served as a hub for these communications, which is accessible at <http://www.linkedin.com/company/probonoh2020/>.

Figure 12: LinkedIn Page

Over this timeframe, the page featured 121 updates, with 62 posts published between M11–M23 and 59 posts from M24–M35. LinkedIn analytics from the past 12 months reflect the page's strong performance, recording an impressive total of 39,332 impressions. This robust engagement underscores the platform's effectiveness in reaching and resonating with a professional audience. Figure 13 offers a comprehensive breakdown of the professional backgrounds of the PROBONO followers on LinkedIn. The data indicates a predominant presence

from industries such as Engineering, Research, Operations, Education, etc. aligning seamlessly with the target audience delineated in D8.1.

Figure 13 - LinkedIn Impressions Rate

Figure 14: Visitor Demographics

3.2.2 X

As an integral component of the Communication and Dissemination strategy, X (formerly Twitter) has served as a complementary platform to LinkedIn, disseminating similar project-related information, which is accessible at <https://twitter.com/probonoh2020>.

Figure 15: X Page

Between M11-M23 and M24-M35, the platform posted 66 and 62 updates, respectively, effectively maintaining a consistent flow of information. Over the past 12 months, X analytics indicate the page achieved 3.6K impressions, showcasing active interaction and dissemination within the platform. This strategic utilization of X aligns with the broader communication strategy, amplifying the project's visibility and outreach across multiple social media channels.

Figure 16: X Impressions Rate

Apart from LinkedIn and X, the PROBONO project initially incorporated two additional social media channels, namely Facebook and Instagram. However, considering their limited relevance and lower popularity within the scope of the H2020 project, a strategic decision was made by the WP8 leader and Communication Committee members to discontinue these platforms. The rationale behind this choice was to concentrate efforts on LinkedIn and X, recognizing these platforms as more conducive to effective promotion and enhanced engagement for the project's objectives. This decision reflects a focused approach, aligning resources with channels that offer greater potential for outreach and impact within the project's target audience.

Further, in addition to refreshing the project website's background photo, the LinkedIn and X profiles have been updated with a cohesive and visually appealing project image, ensuring a consistent and professional look across all communication channels.

3.3 Newsletter

The newsletter serves as a targeted communication tool disseminated from our project to a select list of subscribers who have previously provided consent and expressed interest in receiving updates from PROBONO. As of November 2024, the newsletter boasts a subscriber count of 90 engaged readers.

The project's initial newsletter made its debut in M15, offering an introduction to the consortium and a comprehensive overview of the PROBONO living labs. Among its highlighted content were articles focused on "Green Building Neighbourhoods" concept and the pivotal role of social perspective and practicalities in success of any project. Impressively, the newsletter achieved a perfect delivery rate, ensuring it reached its intended audience. Furthermore, it garnered substantial engagement, boasting total opens of 45 and a notable 33.3% click-through rate per unique open. These metrics signify a robust interest and active engagement among readers, underscoring the newsletter's effectiveness in disseminating critical insights and project updates within the PROBONO initiative.

For context, industry benchmarks indicate that the average click-through rate across all industries is approximately [2.62%](#). This comparison highlights the PROBONO newsletter's exceptional performance, reflecting strong interest and active engagement among readers. Such metrics underscore the newsletter's effectiveness in disseminating critical insights and project updates within the PROBONO initiative.

The second newsletter of the project has been released in M22 which announced the participation of PROBONO at ENLIT Europe 2023. Additionally, the newsletter featured article on "How Digital Tools can Facilitate Citizen Engagement", "Knowledge Graphs' Ontologies and Applications for Energy Efficiency in Buildings" and a video by Aarhus Living Lab on ProBIM tool, an ingenious solution that is currently under development. The newsletter had a 100% rate of successful deliveries with a total open of 62 and 16.67% clicks per unique open.

The third newsletter, issued in M28, introduced the project's official video and podcast on the "Green Building Neighbourhood Concept by PROBONO H2020." This edition also unveiled updated and comprehensive Living Lab webpages while featuring updates from sister projects [ARV](#) and [oPEN Lab](#). With 104 total opens and a 20% click-through rate per unique open, the newsletter continued to effectively disseminate project milestones and foster community interest.

In M35, the fourth newsletter showcased a diverse range of topics, including articles on "Addressing Trust Issues in Digital Twins," "Corporations, Sustainability and CSR," "PROBONO Develops Drone-Based Methods for Mapping Embedded CO₂ in Existing Buildings", etc. Updates from sister projects such as [WeForming](#), [InEExS](#), ARV, oPEN Lab and [ENERGATE](#) further enriched the content. With 60 total opens and a significant 38.24% click-through rate per unique open, this edition reflects a promising trajectory for engagement as the newsletter continues to establish its reach.

WELCOME TO THE PROBONO H2020 PROJECT

Building Green and Sustainable Neighbourhood by Using the Power of Social Engagement and Technology!

Dear PROBONO Pioneers,

As society becomes increasingly urban and ever dependent on technological innovations, it is vital to ensure that people and planet are put at the very heart of this development in a way that is sensitive to and encourages the protection, expansion or re-introduction of sustainable space amongst the urban sprawl.

This is the aim of the PROBONO project. PROBONO has an initial focus on renovating existing urban buildings and locations in a resource and energy efficient way. Applying technology, business and socio-economic innovations to stimulate a transition to net-zero and energy positive buildings, leading to a better understanding of how these sustainable renovations can be a catalyst to create a wider, more sustainable Green Building Neighbourhoods and thus, thriving and sustainable community.

About the Project

The PROBONO project envisions establishing a people-focused European construction industry, by working in harmony with the broader community of stakeholders, to deliver scalable, sustainable, and viable energy-positive and zero-carbon Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs). The objective of the project is to produce validated solutions for the design, construction, and operation of zero-emission and positive-energy buildings in sustainable green neighbourhoods. For achieving this vision and objective, PROBONO will deliver five GBN Transition Acceleration Enablers deployed in six high-impact and people-focused Living Labs (LLs) across six EU states. These GBN Living Labs will include two municipality-driven large-scale demonstrators (Madrid and Dublin) and four living labs representing business/owner promoters of the GBN transition (Porto, Brussels, Aarhus, Prague).

[VISIT OUR WEBSITE](#)

Figure 17 - Newsletter Header

Online version of all PROBONO H2020 Newsletters are located at:

<https://www.probonoh2020.eu/reports>

3.4 Press Releases

According to the DoA, the PROBONO project was mandated to publish a total of 10 press releases by the project's conclusion. Impressively, as of M35, the project has successfully dispatched 30 press releases associated with the PROBONO project. These releases encompassed a diverse range of media platforms, such as corporate websites, online newspapers, business portals, etc. A detailed breakdown of all the press releases up to M35 can be found in Table 2, outlining the comprehensive coverage and dissemination achieved by the project.

Name	Link
SERCO in the PROBONO project	https://www.serco.com/eu/sector-expertise/international-organisations/probono-project
SIN in the PROBONO project	https://smartinnovationnorway.com/en/nyheter/smart-innovation-norway-as-wins-a-new-horizon-2020-project-in-tough-competition/
IDOM in the PROBONO project	https://www.idom.com/en/new/idom-is-part-of-the-probono-project-within-the-h2020-program/
ACC in the PROBONO project	https://www.acciona.com/updates/news/european-commission-to-cofinance-acciona-led-probono-project-as-part-of-horizon-2020-program/?_adin=02021864894
CARTIF in the PROBONO project	https://www.cartif.es/en/probono-buildings-neighbourhoods-examples-sustainability-energy-efficiency/
PNO in the PROBONO project	https://www.innovationplace.eu/project/pro-bono-pillars-for-realising-outcomes-from-buildings-of-negative-output-towards-innovative-and-energy-positive-buildings-in-green-neighbourhood-networks/1810
EcoForest in the PROBONO project	https://ecoforest.com/de/nachrichten/ecoforest-will-be-part-of-the-probono-project/

UCD in the PROBONO project	https://www.ucd.ie/buildingenergyinformatics/projects/probono/
TUC in PROBONO project	https://www.ember.tuc.gr/en/research/horizon-probono
KNT in PROBONO project	https://konnecta.io/projects/probono
EUR in PROBONO project	https://www.eur.nl/en/news/researchers-win-horizon-2020-grant-green-building-neighborhoods
eBOS in PROBONO project	https://ebos.com.cy/probono-the-integrator-centric-approach-for-realising-innovative-energy-efficient-buildings-in-connected-sustainable-green-neighbourhoods/
Aarhus in PROBONO project	https://digit.au.dk/research-projects/probono
INLE in PROBONO project	https://inlecom.gr/portfolio/probono/
AKKA in PROBONO project	https://www.akka-technologies.com/app/uploads/en-akka-probono.pdf
The Integrator-centric approach for realising innovative energy efficient buildings in connected sustainable green neighbourhoods	https://www.rhc-platform.org/project/the-integrator-centric-approach-for-realising-innovative-energy-efficient-buildings-in-connected-sustainable-green-neighbourhoods/
PROBONO PST in Madrid	https://www.probonoh2020.eu/post/successful-probono-pst-meeting-in-madrid
PROBONO in ENLIT	https://www.enlit-europe.com/exhibitor-press-releases/probono-h2020-project-participate-enlit-europe-2023-conference

PROBONO in ENLIT	https://www.innovationplace.eu/news/probono-h2020-project-at-enlit-europe-2023
PROBONO in ENLIT	https://www.cartif.es/en/events/probono-enlit-europe-2023-conference/
PROBONO in ENLIT	https://gbcroatia.org/en/projekt-probono-h2020-sudjeluje-na-konferenciji-enlit-europe-2023/
PROBONO Madrid LL	https://www.livinlastablas.com/2023/11/madrid-nuevo-norte-experimentara-en-las.html
ITA in PROBONO GA meeting	https://www.itainnova.es/blog/noticias/itainnova-participa-en-probono-para-impulsar-la-construccion-y-renovacion-de-edificios-de-forma-eficiente-en-terminos-energeticos-y-de-recursos-materiales/
PROBONO GA in Chania	https://www.kriti24.gr/synantisi-ton-etairon-toy-ergoy-horizon-2020-probono-sto-kam-sta-kania/
PROBONO GA in Chania	https://kriti360.gr/synantisi-ton-etairon-toy-ergoy-horizon-2020-probono-sto-kam-sta-kania/
PROBONO GA in Chania	https://cretavoice.gr/synantisi-ton-etairon-tou-ergou-horizon-2020-probono-sto-kam/
Rooftop garden initiative promotes sustainability and community engagement	https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/environment-and-climate/european-green-deal/green-deal-projects-support/green-deal-success-stories/rooftop-garden-initiative-promotes-sustainability-and-community-engagement
Harmonizing innovation and sustainability: The PROBONO Project's vision for Green	https://www.enlit.world/projects-zone/harmonizing-innovation-and-sustainability-the-probono-projects-vision-for-green-building-neighbourhoods/

Building Neighbourhoods	
For a more sustainable world. With the European PROBONO project, we are making progress in urban regeneration	https://www.idom.com/en/new/for-a-more-sustainable-world-with-the-european-probono-project-we-are-making-progress-in-urban-regeneration/
PROBONO Energy Community Policy	https://www.acciona.com/updates/articles/acciona-organizes-workshop-district-networks-sustainable-energy-communities/

Table 2 - Press Releases

3.5 Scientific Publications

Table 3 presents the scientific publications that were accepted for submission up to M35. These publications are available online and all of them are publicly accessible.

Partner Name	Type of paper	Description and DOI
TUC	Review Paper	Lygerakis, F.; Kampelis, N.; Kolokotsa, D. Knowledge Graphs' Ontologies and Applications for Energy Efficiency in Buildings: A Review. <i>Energies</i> 2022 , <i>15</i> , 7520. https://doi.org/10.3390/en15207520
INLE	Conference Paper	Trusted DBL: A Blockchain-based Digital Twin for Sustainable and Interoperable Building Performance Evaluation https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9854287
TUC	Conference Paper	Kampelis, N.; Lygerakis, F.; Kolokotsa, D. Towards the development of a knowledge graph-based decision support framework for Green Building Neighbourhoods, 6th International Conference on Countermeasures to Urban Heat Islands (IC2UHI), pp. 1–11. ©2023, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. https://www.ic2uhi2023.com/proceedings
AU	Conference paper	Schultz, C., Zayed, Y., Kristoffersen, A.E., Lohm, G., & Kamari, A. (2023). Towards a human-centred framework for representing and reasoning about social values in buildings. In EG-ICE 2023 (the 30th International Workshop on Intelligent Conference), London, UK: https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/construction/sites/bartlett_construction/files/towards_a_human-centred_framework_for_representing_and_reasoning_about_social_values_in_buildings.pdf
MM	Research Paper	Luc, J. (2024). Using Large Language Models for a standard assessment mapping for sustainable communities. arXiv preprint arXiv:2411.00208. https://arxiv.org/abs/2411.00208v2

AU	Journal paper	Kristoffersen, A.E., Schultz, C., & Kamari, A. (2024). Critical Comparison of Concepts and Approaches to Social Sustainability between Existing Academic Literature and Building Certification Systems. <i>Journal of Building Engineering</i> .
AU	Conference paper	Zayed, Y., Kristoffersen, A.E., Lohm, G., Kamari, A., & Schultz, C. (2024). The anatomy of an architect's argument: Formally capturing socially-oriented design intentions in the built environment. In EC3 2024 (European Council on Computing in Construction) conference, Chania, Crete, Greece.
AU	Extended abstract with poster (presented at a conference)	Kristoffersen, A.E., Petersen, S., & Kamari, A. (2023). Comparison of social quality criteria in building sustainability certification systems. In LCM 2023 (The 11th International Conference on Life Cycle Management), Lille, France. https://pure.au.dk/portal/en/publications/comparison-of-social-quality-criteria-in-building-sustainability-
MM	Technical note, code and dataset	Jonveaux, L. (2024). Using Generative AI to accelerate Green Building Neighbourhoods assessments using the ISO 37100 series and LLMs. (1.0.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14216013

Table 3 - Scientific Publications

3.6 Videos

In M23, a project video was developed to introduce the PROBONO project to the various stakeholders. Focused on providing an overview of the project's vision and objectives, the video serves as a valuable tool for dissemination efforts.

Figure 18: Project Video

Its creation commenced in M21 under SIN's guidance, followed by rigorous editing and review processes overseen by the GBN Committee and Communication Committee members. The video (<https://youtu.be/94GwKp1YIDo?feature=shared>) is available on the project's YouTube channel and has been promoted on project website and SM channels in M24.

Another addition to the PROBONO YouTube channel is a video spotlighting ProBIM, an innovative solution currently in development. Crafted by Aarhus University, this video serves to elucidate the functionality and objectives of this pioneering tool within the PROBONO project. Its purpose is to provide a comprehensive understanding of ProBIM and its potential applications, offering stakeholders insight into the ongoing advancements within the initiative.

The project YouTube channel also features a video showcasing the ProFormalise tool, an innovative solution from the Aarhus Living Lab. This tool empowers architects to seamlessly incorporate social values into their building designs while ensuring these values are clearly communicated to stakeholders through the building information model (BIM). By establishing logical connections between design elements, products, and social value objectives, ProFormalise fosters transparency and alignment, enabling thoughtful design choices that enhance societal impact.

Following their upload to the PROBONO YouTube channel, the videos will/has been strategically promoted across multiple channels for wider accessibility. This strategic approach includes prominent showcasing on the project's official website, active dissemination across various social media platforms, and inclusion in public newsletters. Through these deliberate dissemination efforts, the project's video content is intended to reach a diverse audience, fostering increased engagement and deeper comprehension of the project's goals and achievements.

3.7 Communication Kit

The communication kit serves as a comprehensive collection of materials aimed at promoting the PROBONO project. Some components were previously outlined in D8.1 and D8.15. In addition to these, a dedicated project PowerPoint specifically highlighting the PROBONO project has been created.

Figure 19 - Project Presentation

This PowerPoint deck is designed to furnish the consortium with concise yet detailed project information, intended for utilization in meetings and external events with partners. Its purpose is to ensure uniform and coherent communication, fostering consistency across engagements. Besides project ppt, a new roll up (v2) and project stickers (See Appendix I & II) were designed for the purpose of promoting the project in various international and national events. All of the project promotional materials are readily accessible to all partners within the PROBONO repository, facilitating easy access and utilization for effective project promotion.

4 Impact of Communication and Dissemination Activities in the second and third reporting periods

Table 4 has been crafted based on the initial Key Performance Indicator (KPI) targets outlined in the Description of Action (DoA) and D8.1. Comprising four columns, the first two columns specify the target location, and the corresponding metrics measured. Following these details, it delineates the targeted goals by M60 alongside the current progress status as of M35. To enhance clarity, the final column is color-coded. Here, green indicates that we're on track, yellow shows we're making progress, and red signifies a delay in meeting the set targets.

Target description		Target Goal (M60)	M35	Status
Website	N° of page visits to the website	500	3670	
	N° of references to the project on search engines	120	1821	
Social Media Channels	N° of contacts/followers on social media	300/200	770	
Press materials	N° of press releases	10	30	
	N° of articles	10	23	
Videos	N° of views on the video	1000	449	
Events	N° of participants in the final project conference	200	n/a	n/a
	N° of conferences as speaker	6	18	
	N° of conferences with PROBONO presentations	10	27	
Promotional and marketing materials	N° of printing materials	1	5	

Newsletter	N° of subscribers	500	90	
	N° of Newsletters sent	8	4	
	Open rate	60%	68%	
Academic Publications	N° of published academic publications	8	9	
Workshops & Roundtables	N° of workshops as co-organizer	4	3	

Table 4 - KPI List

5 Conclusion and Next Steps

The D8.2 report provides a thorough analysis of the alignment between PROBONO's initial commitments and its tangible achievements, with a specific focus on the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) strategy outlined in D8.1. This comprehensive analysis evaluates the project's progress up to M35, offering insights for enhancement based on feedback and measurements from Reporting Period II and III. In essence, the report functions as a detailed roadmap, highlighting the project's objectives, accomplishments, and proposed strategies to disseminate its achievements across diverse target audiences.

As the project concludes its third year and moves into the fourth, the focus shifts to the next phase of activities for M36 to M42. While all KPIs for the preceding period have been successfully met, the upcoming phase prioritizes strengthening the visibility and outreach of the Living Labs and Social Innovation initiatives. These areas will serve as focal points for the project's continued efforts, with enhanced plans to update the CERNA webpage in collaboration with WP2 and Living Lab Leaders. This collaboration aims to ensure the webpage reflects the latest project developments and data, offering a more comprehensive resource for stakeholders.

Further, as the project advances and incorporates an array of tools and IT technologies, the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) activities will also pivot towards highlighting the visibility and impact of these innovations within the project. This strategic focus on showcasing these tools will be channelled through the Enablers webpage, which will include expanded content specifically discussing these advancements. Moreover, the technical partners within the project are set to contribute articles spotlighting various IT tools and technologies that are currently in use or planned for implementation within the PROBONO project. These articles will provide in-depth insights into the functionalities and applications of these technological assets, enriching the project's communication efforts.

References

PROBONO Project . (2021). *PROPOSAL_101037075-PROBONO-H2020-LC-GD-2020-7-PART_B_Section_1*.

Ismaylzada, S. (2022). *PROBONO D8.5 PROBONO Alliance Liaison (I)*. Retrieved from https://www.probonoh2020.eu/_files/ugd/4d6f38_1d9cd18a781f4006a25867049a5a8e75.pdf

Ismaylzada, S. (2022). *PROBONO D8.1 Dissemination and communication strategy & reporting (I)*. Retrieved from https://www.probonoh2020.eu/_files/ugd/4d6f38_1dacbbf712d247f09f871943ade03e40.pdf

Appendix

Appendix I

Figure 20 - PROBONO Roll up v2

Appendix II

Figure 21 - PROBONO Sticker v1